

Laboratory Investigation of Bituminous Concrete Mixes Utilizing Pond Ash

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Abstract: Bituminous concrete is one of the most expensive and costly flexible pavement layers used in surface courses. Despite their high material cost, bituminous mixes are efficiently proposed to satisfy engineering objectives like as stability and durability. Mineral filler passing through a 0.075 mm is an important component in bituminous mixes. The Asphalt Institute suggests incorporating 4-8% filler in asphalt concrete. In India, common filler materials such as cement, lime stone, granite particles, and so on are harder to find and costly as well. In India, pond ash is supposed to be less costly and more accessible. The goal of this research is to assess the effect of pond ash mineral filler on the behaviour of bituminous concrete mixes. For the comparison, the Marshall mixture design approach was used. The Marshall stabilities of mixes including 25, 50, 75, and 100 percent pond ash (PSMF) and conventional mineral filler (IBPMPFO) were found to be 18.57KN, 18.64KN, 18.89KN, 18.78KN, and 23.16 KN, respectively, meeting the Marshall Design minimum criterion of 9 KN. The study implies that PSMF might be utilized as a mineral filler in bituminous mixes.

IndexTerms – Pond Ash, Mineral Filler Stability, Marshall Quotient

I. INTRODUCTION

Asphalt roads are ones that make use of bitumen as a binder. It consists of a compact mixture that includes aggregates, mineral filler, and bitumen. The kind and amount of mineral filler material used influences the quality and sustainability of bituminous roads. The mineral filler stiffens the bituminous cement since it is finely dispersed in it [1]. Cement, lime, granite powder, stone dust, and fine sand are popular fillers used in bituminous mixes. Cement, quarry stone dust, lime, and granite stone dust are more expensive but may be used more effectively for various purposes. Stone dust, fly ash, and building waste dust finer than 0.075 mm filter size seemed to be excellent filler materials. Several research studies have focused on the use of industrial byproducts as mineral fillers in bituminous mixes in recent years. Phosphate waste mineral filler (MF) [2], Jordanian oil shale fly ash (SFA) [3] [4], bag house fines (BHF) [5] [6], municipal solid waste ash (MSWA) [7], and ceramic waste [7] have all been tested as fillers. It was discovered that several forms of recycled filler may be used in bituminous mixes to improve performance. As a result, the current study was conducted to assess the performance of bituminous mixes using Pond ash mineral filler (PSMF). When filler is mixed with less bitumen than is required to fill the air gaps, it produces a stiff, dry product that is virtually unusable. In contrast, overfilling with bitumen imparts a flow aspect to the mixture. The filler can increase particle resistance to movement within the mix matrix and/or act as an ingredient when it interacts with bituminous cement, modifying the mastic's properties [8]. The use of mineral filler can increase the elastic modulus of a bituminous concrete mixture [9]. However, using too much filler might weaken the mixture by increasing the amount of bitumen necessary to lubricate the stones [10] [11]. Gradations can have an impact on the effectiveness of these fillers.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Materials

The aggregate gradation [13] in our research work is summarized in Table 1.

In this investigation, the VG-30-viscosity grade from the MRPL oil refinery was used [14]. The properties of VG-30 bitumen are presented in Table 2.

2.2 Objectives and methodology

The study work's aims are to analyze the potentiality of molding industry by-products as mineral fillers (PSMF) in Bituminous concrete mid limit grade 2 mixes by laboratory examination. Marshall volumetric (Voids analysis) and mechanistic characteristics (stability and flow) of BC-2 mixtures containing 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 percent PSMF were also examined [12].

Table 1. Aggregate gradation for Bituminous concrete grading – 2 mixtures

IS Sieve size (mm)	Range of gradation	Percentage Retained on sieve sizes (Mid limit)	Percent of PSMF content
19	100	10.5	
13.2	79-100	10.5	
9.5	70-88	17	
4.75	53-71	12	
2.36	42-58	9	
1.18	34-48	9	
0.6	26-38	9	
0.3	18-28	7	
0.15	12-20	9	
0.075	4-10	7	0, 25, 50, 75 & 100

Table 2. Properties of VG-30

Description	Results
Penetration value @ 25°C, 0.1mm	68.33
Softening point in °C	51.75
Ductility value @ 27 °C in cm	82.5
Specific gravity(Sp.gr) @ 27 °C	1.00
Flash Point in °C	260.0
Viscosity test @ 135°C in cst	390.0

Table 3. Physical properties of materials

Test	Test Results
Sp.Gr. of PSMF	2.11
Specific surface area of PSMF, cm ² /gm	2914
Specific surface area of Cement, cm ² /gm	3181
Specific surface area of stone MF, cm ² /gm	2838

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the Marshal Experiments on bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures prepared with varying industrial by-product percentage by pond ash mineral filler (PSMF) are presented in Table 5. The optimal binder content was selected from the test results for bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures using 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 percent pond ash mineral fillers. The effect of pond ash mineral fillers on the different parameters of bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures has been described in the following sections.

Table 4 Mixture Parameters relative to 4 percent air voids for PSMF

Marshall Parameters	Type of MF	PSMF content, Percentage				
		0	25	50	75	100
Optimal bitumen content, %	PSMF	5.48	5.50	5.53	5.59	5.63
Air voids, %	PSMF	4.17	4.09	4.06	4.11	4.14
Marshall Stability, KN	PSMF	23.16	18.57	18.64	18.89	18.78
Flow, mm	PSMF	3.63	3.70	3.86	3.98	4.10
Bulk Density, g/cc	PSMF	2.37	2.36	2.36	2.35	2.35
Voids in Mineral Aggregates, %	PSMF	17.18	17.23	17.09	16.93	16.48
Voids Filled with Bitumen, %	PSMF	75.75	75.80	75.27	75.68	76.87
Theoretical Specific Density, g/cc	PSMF	2.48	2.48	2.46	2.44	2.39
Marshall Quotient, KN/mm	PSMF	6.37	6.41	6.52	6.71	6.89

3.1 Effect of PSMF on optimal bitumen content

As shown in table 5, the optimal bitumen content (OBC) of mixtures, designed with 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 percent PSMF. The OBC assessed using 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 per cent of IBP-MF shows a similar pattern as the PSMF content in the BC-2 mixture increases and the OBC increases. It is also identified that the OBC referring to 4 per cent air void is marginally higher for BC-2 mixtures with 25, 50, 75 and 100 per cent PSMF compared to BC-2 mixtures with 0 per cent IBP-MF. This may be due to higher specific surface area of PSMF particle in mixture increased the OBC when compared to traditional material.

3.2 Effect of PSMF on Marshall Stability value

It is observed from the table 5 that the BC-2 mixtures using PSMF showed lower stability value as the PSMF content in the BC-2 mixture increases. It is also found that the stability value lower for BC-2 mixtures with 25, 50, 75 and 100 per cent PSMF compared to BC-2 mixtures with traditional mixtures (0 percent IBPMF).

3.3 Effect of PSMF on Flow value

Table 5 showing the variation of flow value with 0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 per cent of PSMF. It is found that the Flow value of mixture increase as the PSMF increases in the BC-2 mixture. This is because of high specific surface area particle replacing particle of traditional material with lower specific area in the mixture.

3.4 Effect of PSMF on Bulk Density

The effect of PSMF on the bulk density of the compacted BC-2 mixtures is shown in the table 5. BC-2 mixtures with PSMF content has decreased bulk density values compare to traditional mineral filler material. This is due to fact that the specific gravity of pond ash mineral filler and theoretical specific gravity of mixture are lower than the BC-2 mixture with traditional materials (cement and stone dust).

IV. CONCLUSION

The following are some insights from the investigation of the mixture design characteristics of bituminous mixtures utilizing PSMF, and traditional materials.

- Pond ash mineral filler has increased the optimal bitumen content of bituminous concrete mixtures due to its high specific surface area.
- The bituminous concrete mixture containing PSMF has significantly increased the optimal bitumen content, which increases the cost of production compare to bituminous concrete mixture of traditional material.
- The incorporation of PSMF to the grade-2 mixture of bituminous concrete satisfied Marshall Stability requirement as per Ministry of Road Transport and Highways 4th Revision specification.

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